

Research

MA-CNN: Multi-augmented data classification using 2D-CNN with kaiming initialization for environmental sound classification

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Abstract: In the field of audio classification, speech recognition or environmental sound classification, the performance has been greatly improved using deep learning based systems, but is still a challenge where comes small scale corpora training as the deep learning based systems need a huge amount of training data and it is not easy to get that much data. For this problem, this paper proposed a solution of multi-augmented data classification using convolutional neural network with kaiming initialization for limited resources (MA-CNN). The contributions of this work are twofold. First we propose a 2-dimension convolutional neural network with kaiming initialization, using only convolutional and fully connected layers. This prevent the neural network from exploding in the forward pass process. Secondly, to avoid data scarcity, over-fitting and to improve model robustness, we used multiple data augmentation techniques that increased training data quantity. The proposed methodology outperformed CNN without data augmentation technique.

Keywords: Data augmentation, Deep neural networks, Environmental sound classification, Kaiming initialization, Limited resources

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Introduction

Environmental sound classification (ESC) is a topic of great significance in current era in the field of sound classification and has received quite an attention for over few years. The processing of environmental sound is different than music or speech because the frequency time modulation of environmental sound is way too complicated. The applications of ESC include remote surveillance ^[1], source identification, audio tag identification, home automation, and so on. The diversity of sound instances make ESC more complicated than ASR. Different machine learning algorithms, including KNN ^[2] and SVM ^[3] have previously been used to process features including linear prediction coefficients (LPC), perceptual linear prediction (PLP) ^[3] and mel frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) ^[4] but with these

approaches, the performance is still unsatisfactory as the traditional classification algorithms lacks deep feature extraction ability [3].

Up till now, there are several audio classification techniques to improve development in the field of ESC, including dictionary learning [5], and wavelet filterbanks, but there is still an unfilled space for improvement in the field of ESC. Deep learning techniques, in particular, CNN have made a great improvement in the last few years in the field of audio classification (ESC) [6]. When deep learning models are applied with inputs like spectrograms, they capture patterns like energy modulation across frequency and time. This attribute of the deep learning model is considered as an important quality for distinguishing different sounds such as gunshot or dog bark.

Deep learning technique especially CNN performed better than dictionary learning approach with spectrograms as extracted features, representing classes in a specific audio topic with noisy audio samples where traditional MFCC fails to achieve expected accuracy but there is still a gap to improve the performance of CNN in the respective field [5][7].

For training deep learning models, a huge amount of data is required. Practically, it is quite difficult to acquire such huge amount of training data and results with small training data are not good enough [8]. Using small dataset for training deep learning models result in overfitting [9]. Small sampled audio classification is immature which make it a great challenge for deep learning models to train in limited resource scenarios [10].

Our paper presents a solution to limited resource dataset for deep learning models in the field of ESC. Data augmentation technique is one of possible solutions to this problem. Data augmentation works on the concept of deformations on labeled data. This deformation do not change the semantical meaning of classes, for example, even after time shift data augmentation, a drill sound will remain drill sound [11]. Data augmentation increase data quantity. By training networks on this deformed data, the networks does not change against these deformations and get trained for testing on unseen validation data [12]. Data augmentation creates virtual points of data using original data from dataset. This is used to train the deep learning network with imbalance dataset handling and reduce overfitting.

Our method (MA-CNN) propose an innovation in the field of ESC by simplification of CNN and achieving good results with low resource training dataset. In MA-CNN, we introduced kaiming initialization of weights in a 2D-CNN network with the combination of multiple data augmentation techniques to tackle limited training dataset for neural network processing. Our proposed model with combination of data augmentation yield good results.

Related Work

ESC has received much attention in the past few years. Researchers have performed works on environmental sound classification. A study [12] proposed a dilated CNN in the field of environmental sound classification, achieving accuracy of 78 %. Another study [7] proposed a convolutional neural network with combination of data augmentation in ESC task, yielding accuracy of 79 % accuracy rate. This study compared their results based on data augmentation with results of the same network on same data without data augmentation and achieved accuracy of 74 %. [3] achieved accuracy of 83.7 % by using stacked convolutional neural network with mixup method to generate training data. Another study [9] used limited dataset to train convolutional neural network based on transfer learning and data augmentation.

Preliminaries

The ability of neural network to study and learn spectrum-patterns make deep learning techniques a perfect fit for environmental sound classification, but when it comes to training deep learning algorithms, the data should be large enough to perform deep training. For limited resources in such scenarios where the training data is not enough, our proposed study has the following contributions.

1. A 2-dimensional convolutional neural network with kaiming initialization is proposed for training and testing. This technique resulted in a new algorithm that only used a convolutional layer and fully connected layer by ignoring max pooling layer.
2. Multi data augmentation technique is used to tackle the over-fitting problem, data scarcity and to improve model robustness. This technique increased data quantity for limited training dataset.

The advantage of kaiming initialization is prevention of shattering or dispersion of output from activation layer in the forward propagation in NN. In case of shattering or dispersion, the gradient loss will either be too large or too small to flow backwards. In such case, the neural network will take a very long time to converge only if the network is able to do so.

Methodology

Data Augmentation

We performed multiple experiments on data to see the modulation of model accuracy. The block diagram of MA-CNN is shown in figure 1. We used 2 different data augmentation techniques, including time-shift and time-frequency masking directly on the audio (raw data) as well as extracted feature samples. We explained each data augmentation technique as follows:

1. Time Shift: It is a simple data augmentation technique that just shift the audio to left or right with some random amount of time by adding random time before or after the audio signal.
2. Time and Frequency Masking: In computer vision, time masking and frequency masking is similar to cutout data augmentation. A randomly chosen time stamp slice or frequency bands are masked with the mean value of spectrogram.
 - a. Frequency masking: A range of succeeding frequencies are masked out using frequency masking technique. In a spectrogram, horizontal bars are added to achieve frequency masking.
 - b. Time mask: Frequency mask and time mask is a bit similar, besides that in spectrogram, the range of time is randomly blocked out by using vertical bars.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of MA-CNN

Feature Extraction

In deep learning, models rarely take raw audio as direct input. Commonly, raw data is converted into spectrogram. Spectrogram is a compact picture of an audio signal and since audio spectrogram is an image, it is a good fit to be used as input in CNN based models created for processing images. Fourier transforms (FT) of audio signals are used to generate spectrograms. Fourier transform works on the concept of decomposition where audio signals are decomposed into its integral frequencies, and then displaying the frequency amplitude in the signal.

Spectrogram split the span of an audio signal into smaller time segments. FT of each segment is applied to calculate the frequencies of each segment and combines the FT of all segments in a single graph. Spectrogram plot time on x-axis and frequency on y-axis using different colors on the plot. Bright colored areas on the plot indicate high energy of audio signal as shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2: Spectrogram of audio signal

For processing audio data under deep learning, conversion of audio or augmented audio into spectrograms is the best way that captures the most important and unique features of audio signals.

Convolutional Neural Network

Neural networks are sub-type of machine learning, and they are at the heart of deep learning algorithms [13]. A neural network consists of node layers that contain nodes, input layer, one or more hidden layers and an output layer. Each node is interconnected with every other node. Every node has its own threshold and weight [14]. A specific node activation occurs when the output of an individual node exceeds the marked threshold value and that sends data to next layer.

Convolutional neural networks (CNN) are deep neural networks that are used to process image, audio or speech signals. A typical CNN comprises of three main layers: convolutional layer, pooling layer (ignored in Kaiming Initialization technique) and fully connected layer. Convolutional layer is the core building block of CNN. Most of computations occurs in this layer. Convolutional layer consists of input data, filter and a feature map. Convolutions take place in convolutional layer, given by equation 1.

$$I(x, y) = \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^m k(i, j)I(x + i, y + j)$$

Where k is the kernel with the size of image $n \times m$.

The process of convolution allows a feature detector or filter to move across the data to check the presence of feature. The size of a typical filter is 3×3 that determines the size of the data field. This filter is then applied to the area of respective image feature and a dot product of filter and input image pixels is calculated. The resultant of product is fed in output array of same dimension. This whole process is repeated along the entire image after the kernel is changed by a step. The final output shapes into a series of dot products from input layer and filter, known as activation map or feature map.

Before training neural network over input data, hyperparameters are set that affect the size of output.

- Number of filters, which affect the output depth.
- Stride is the number of pixels, over which the kernel moves across the input matrix.
- Zero padding is used when the kernel do not fit the input image matrix. Valid padding, full padding or same padding is applied in such cases.

At the end of each convolution, Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) transformation is applied by CNN to the activation map, introducing non-linearity to the model, defined as $y = \max(0, x)$ (Figure 3).

Fig. 3: Rectified Linear Unit

Input image pixels are not connected to output layer directly in partially connected layers. In fully connected layer, each node of the output layer is directly connected to the nodes in its previous layer. Fully connected layer performs classification on the basis of features extracted using previous layers and feature detectors. Convolutional layer tend to use ReLu transformation for non-linearity, while fully connected layer uses softmax activation function for input classification with probability from 0 to 1, given as (Equation 2):

$$softmax(x_i) = \frac{\exp(x_i)}{\sum_j \exp(x_j)}$$

Where x is the values from the neurons of the output layer and exponential acts as the non-linear function.

Kaiming Initialization

A sound initialization method was first introduced in [14] by *Kaiming He*. Kaiming Initialization, or He Initialization, is a weight initialization method for neural networks that takes into account the non-linearity of activation functions, such as ReLU activations. The continuous modeling ReLu non-linearity make deep learning models to converge, given by the equation 3.

$$std = \sqrt{\frac{2}{(1 + a^2)fan_{in}}}$$

Where a is the negative slope of this rectifier layer and fan_{in} is the number of input dimensions for forward propagation and fan_{out} is used for backward propagation. By default, a is 0 for ReLU.

ReLU is used as activation function that returns the provided value if input is greater than 0 and return 0 if input is less than 0. In kaiming initialization, the mean is slightly incremented by the weight distribution at each layer and variance close to 1 in forward propagating (Equation 4).

$$y_l = W_l x_l + b_l$$

This stability protects the model from exploding and vanishing in both propagations. Kaiming initialization of weights gives better and stable results as compared to randomly weights initialization. In linear layer initialization, fan_{in} mode is used for forward propagation. In linear layer, the weights are transposed implicitly. The weights initialization is performed with size (out_features, in_features) with transpose. For example, if input size is (a, b). the size of weights would be (b, a). That is why, transpose is performed in linear layer before further operations.

Experiments and results

For the evaluation of proposed CNN method along with the influence of multiple data augmentation techniques, we performed experiments on UrbanSound8K dataset. This dataset consists of 8732 labeled audio files, segmented in 10 different classes including dog bark, children playing, street music, jackhammer, engine idling, air conditioner, siren, car horn, drilling and gun shot. This dataset is simultaneously audio-based, publicly available, and contains several instances of audio samples against different multiple environmental sounds used for sound classification. This dataset is used to compare the results of proposed method with previously used approaches on same dataset including dilated convolutions^[12], deep CNN with data augmentation^[7], and stacked convolutional with mixup to ESC tasks^[3].

The first step of system design is its data preprocessing, to make it ready for use. Most of audio samples in dataset are stereo tracks that recorded two different channels while some of them are mono tracks, recorded with single channel. Our designed model process all signals with same channels and same dimensions. The majority of audio data in dataset has sample rate of 44100Hz while a few of them have 48000Hz of sampling frequency. This means that the array size of all audio files are not same. To make them having same dimensions, the conversion of audio signals into stereo and standardization and conversion all sound files to same sampling frequency resulted in signals with same dimensions and same array size for processing with same size (length).

Time shift data augmentation is applied on the processed raw data and feature spectrograms are extracted of augmented raw data. Over fitting and data scarcity is tackled by applying data augmentation using time and frequency masking on extracted features to improve data quantity, robustness.

Our data is comprised of images of spectrogram, so we created a 2 dimensional convolutional neural network with kaiming initialization to process spectrogram features. The designed model has four convolutional blocks that resulted in activation maps. The processed data is input in linear classifier layer for the prediction of given classes. The parameters of the designed model are as follow:

- The model process start with data input in model. A batch of image spectrograms are input in model with shape (16,2,24,344).
- Convolutional neural network layers applied filters for image depth escalation. Kernels are applied to reduce image height and width. The output feature map of shape (16,64,4,22) is resulted after passing through all four layers.
- The feature map is flattened to (16,64) for linear layer that outputs a prediction score in accordance with each class.

The data is splitted in 70:30 ratio, resulting in training and validation data. The model is trained on data batch for 10 epochs. Optimizer, loss and scheduler are defined, allowing training process to converge in minimum epochs. To converge model training in fewer epochs, we defined loss function to dynamically vary learning rate as training progress. Figure 4 shows the degradation of loss as the model trains.

Fig. 4: Loss decrement for MA-CNN

For evaluation of model, experiments are performed on processed data. For measuring the accuracy of our predictive model, we used modern evaluation metric accuracy. The trained model is tested on validation data.

Studies including dilated convolutions [12], deep CNN with data augmentation [7], and stacked convolutional with mixup to ESC tasks [3] achieved an accuracy of 78 %, 79 %, and 83.7 %. Our proposed work MA-CNN achieved accuracy of 84.2 %. Table 1 shows a comparison of proposed work with previous studies.

Table 1: Accuracy comparison

Method	Accuracy
MA-CNN	84.2%
Dilated convolutions	78%
Deep CNN without data augmentation	73%
Deep CNN with data augmentation	79%
Stacked convolutional with mixup	83.7%

Conclusion

This paper proposed another solution in addition to literature for limited resource deep learning for environmental sound classification. Results showed that MA-CNN performed good as compared to recent methods for environmental sound classification. MA-CNN is not limited to only environmental sound classification, but can be used in wide range of applications relevant to speech processing or audio problems including automatic speech recognition, human computer interaction or text-to-speech. Future studies should explore its applications with other techniques.

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